

1 **Evaluation of microwave-assisted and pressurized liquid extractions to obtain β -**
2 **D-glucans from mushrooms**

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20 **Abstract**

21 Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) and pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) were
22 compared as advanced technologies to obtain polysaccharides (particularly biologically
23 active β -glucans) from *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Ganoderma lucidum* fruiting bodies.
24 Extraction effectiveness was compared by a full-factorial experimental design
25 (response surface methodology, RSM), using water as extraction solvent. Total
26 carbohydrate content of the obtained extracts and polysaccharide yields were the
27 variable responses investigated, while temperature and extraction time were the
28 experimental factors. Temperature showed stronger influence in the polysaccharide
29 extraction than time. The latter factor slightly affected MAE but not PLE extractions.
30 Optimal conditions within the studied range were determined for each extraction
31 method and species based on the desirability functions. Regarding the polysaccharide
32 composition, the main differences between the species were more quantitative rather
33 than qualitative, since NMR analyses indicated that all extracts contained mainly β - and
34 α -glucans and heteropolysaccharides. Both extraction systems were effective for
35 polysaccharide extraction from mushrooms.

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37 **Keywords:** Microwave-assisted extraction; Pressurized liquid extraction; Response
38 surface methodology; β -D-Glucans; *P. ostreatus*; *G. lucidum*.

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44 **Abbreviations:** MAE (Microwave-assisted extraction), PLE (Pressurized liquid extraction), RSM (Response
45 surface methodology), NMR (Nuclear magnetic resonance), GC-MS (Gas-chromatography coupled to mass
46 spectrometry), B1316PP (1,3-1,6- β -D-glucan from *P. pulmonarius*), CHO (carbohydrates).

47 1. Introduction

48 Since ancient times, oriental cultures consume mushrooms as food and medicine, and
49 their influence has recently been transferred to the occidental people. Mushrooms are
50 good sources of vitamins, minerals, proteins, carbohydrates, phenolic compounds,
51 polyunsaturated fatty acids, high amounts of fibers and specific bioactive compounds
52 (Heleno et al., 2015; Reis, Barros, Martins, & Ferreira, 2012). There are an increasing
53 number of cancer patients consuming mushroom dietary supplements as adjuvant
54 treatment. Many of the beneficial properties of mushroom preparations have been
55 demonstrated by studies *in vitro* and *in vivo* to sustain a scientific base (Hardy, 2008;
56 Ruthes, Smiderle, & Iacomini, 2016; Smiderle, Ruthes, & Iacomini, 2014). Most of the
57 biological activities of mushroom extracts are attributed to their polysaccharides that
58 are recognized by membrane receptors of leukocytes and macrophages, as CR3 and
59 dectin-1, leading to proliferation and differentiation of immune cells (Lull, Wichers, &
60 Savelkoul, 2005; Moradali, Mostafavi, Ghods, & Hedjaroude, 2007; Xia et al., 1999).
61 These activities are responsible for enhancing the innate and cell-mediated immune
62 responses, with the expression of pro-inflammatory genes and consequently, for the
63 induction of antitumoral and bactericidal effects (Ramberg, Nelson, & Sinnott, 2010;
64 Schepetkin & Quinn, 2006). Other biological characteristics ascribed for mushroom
65 polysaccharides are their ability of lowering cholesterol levels in serum by reducing
66 LDL levels and modulating genes related to cholesterol metabolism, *i.e.* over-
67 expression of LDLr RNA, scavenge of bile acids during digestion, etc (Gil-Ramirez et
68 al., 2016; Palanisamy et al., 2014).

69 Fungi synthesize a variety of polysaccharides including heteropolysaccharides rich in
70 mannose, galactose, fucose, and xylose, although the most encountered are glucans.
71 They produce glycogen-like glucans as storage and different β -glucans as structural
72 polysaccharides. These polysaccharides are usually branched (1 \rightarrow 3)(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans,
73 but linear β -glucans and also α/β -glucans have been also isolated from certain

74 mushrooms species (Ruthes, Smiderle, & Iacomini, 2015). These β -glucans have
75 attracted most attention because of their capacity of stimulating the immune system,
76 and studies indicated that such activity is more pronounced when they are in triple helix
77 conformation (Goodridge et al., 2011; Lehtovaara & Gu, 2011). Although
78 polysaccharides are polar molecules being easily dissolved in water or alkaline
79 solutions, some of them are insoluble in these solvents. This is the case of some β -
80 glucans, which require longer periods of extraction or stronger conditions such as
81 higher pressure or temperature (Ruthes et al., 2015).

82 Water at elevated temperature and pressure is an interesting solvent because, under
83 these conditions, water remains in the liquid state and exhibits lower solvent viscosity.
84 Such properties provide effective mass transfer and higher solubility of more
85 hydrophobic compounds (Plaza & Turner, 2015). Two technologies that provide higher
86 pressure and/or temperature above the boiling point of water and keep it in liquid state,
87 are the microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) and pressurized liquid extraction (PLE).
88 These approaches are considered as environmentally friendly technologies due to their
89 higher efficiency and consequently lower energy consumption, apart from lower
90 emission of CO₂ as well as reduced use of pollutant solvents (Li, Fabiano-Tixier, Vian,
91 & Chemat, 2013; Plaza & Turner, 2015). The microwave is a non-contact heat source,
92 which can not only make heating more effective and selective, but also help to
93 accelerate energy transfer, start-up and response to heating control and to reduce
94 thermal gradient (Li et al., 2013). While the pressurized liquid extraction is a method
95 that brings water to subcritical conditions, which enables this solvent to dissolve less
96 polar compounds, because the intermolecular interactions involving hydrogen bonding
97 becomes less pronounced (Plaza & Turner, 2015).

98 At the moment, only a few studies have been carried out to extract mushroom β -
99 glucans using MAE or PLE (Benito-Román, Alonso, Cocero, & Goto, 2016; Chen,
100 Shao, Tao, & Wen, 2015), therefore in this work an experimental design based on

101 response surface methodology (RSM) was developed to compare both technologies
102 and determine the optimal extraction conditions to obtain fractions with high levels of
103 mushroom polysaccharides. Two mushroom species, *Pleurotus ostreatus* and
104 *Ganoderma lucidum*, were utilized since they present different morphology and vary on
105 levels of soluble and insoluble polysaccharides (Bonatti, Karnopp, Soares, & Furlan,
106 2004; Mau, Lin, & Chen, 2001). Both species were extracted using a full factorial
107 experimental design, and the polysaccharide composition of the obtained extracts was
108 determined using NMR, GC-MS, and fluorimetric assays.

109

110 **2. Experimental**

111 **2.1. Fungal material**

112 Fresh fruiting bodies of *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Jacq.) P. Kumm. (commercial Gurelan H-
113 107 strain) were grown in controlled cultivation rooms at CTICH (Centro Tecnológico
114 de Investigación del Champiñón de La Rioja, Autol, Spain) cut in slices, lyophilized and
115 ground until a fine powder was obtained. *Ganoderma lucidum* (Curtis) P. Karst. was
116 cultivated by Juncao Brazil (Taboão da Serra, SP, Brazil) and dried in stove before
117 being cut in small pieces and ground. Because of the woody texture of *G. lucidum* and
118 the drying process used, it was ground in fine pieces instead of powder, generating a
119 material as much homogeneous as possible.

120 **2.2. Microwave-assisted extractions (MAE)**

121 MAE extractions were carried out in a Monowave EXTRA extraction system (Anton
122 Paar GmbH, Graz, Austria). The device included a Monowave 300 operating at a
123 maximum power (850 W) with a frequency of 2,455 MHz, and an autosampler MAS 24
124 (that can perform programmed sequences for automatic analysis of up to 24 single
125 experiments). The system can be operated at a maximum pressure of 3 MPa over the
126 sample vial, depending on the solvent composition, volume and working temperature.
127 The 30 mL extraction tube was filled with 0.5 g of mushroom sample, 15 mL of MilliQ

128 water, and a small magnetic stirrer (under these conditions, the system pressure
129 reached a maximum of 1.5 MPa). It was immediately closed and each tube was
130 prepared at the moment of the extraction. Both species were separately extracted,
131 according to the experimental design described in section 2.4. The sample was kept
132 under magnetic agitation (600 rpm) during extraction. After cooling down to 50°C, the
133 tube was collected and the extract was separated from the residue by centrifugation
134 (10,000 rpm, at 20°C, for 15 min). An aliquot (200 µL) of each extract was separated
135 for total carbohydrate determination and later ethanol (3:1; v/v) was added to the
136 extract to precipitate the polysaccharides, which were recovered as described in
137 section 2.6.

138 **2.3. Pressurized liquid extractions (PLE)**

139 The extractions were performed using an Accelerated Solvent Extractor (ASE) (Dionex
140 Corporation, ASE 350, USA), that operates at a maximum temperature of 200°C. The
141 11 mL extraction cell was loaded with a cellulose filter (Dionex Corporation, USA), filled
142 with a mixture of mushroom sample (0.5 g) and washed sea sand (Panreac, Barcelona,
143 Spain) at the ratio 1:8 (mushroom sample:sea sand, w:w) and closed. Each species
144 was separately extracted according to the experimental design described in section
145 2.4. The sea sand was selected as an inert material to hold the sample inside the
146 extraction cell and to improve efficiency avoiding formation of preferential flow paths.
147 Extraction procedure was carried out in an unique cycle for each condition at a range of
148 10.2-11.7 MPa as follows: the closed cell was filled with MilliQ water, heated-up to a
149 set temperature and static extraction was carried out during the selected minutes with
150 all system valves closed. After this period, the cell was rinsed, the solvent was purged
151 out (120 s) of the cell with N₂ gas and the extract was collected in a vial coupled to the
152 system. After collection, an aliquot (200 µL) of each extract was separated for total
153 carbohydrate determination and ethanol (3:1; v/v) was added to the extract to
154 precipitate the polysaccharides, which were recovered as described in section 2.6.

155 **2.4. Response surface methodology (RSM) experimental design**

156 RSM is a compilation of mathematical and statistical techniques based on the fit of a
157 polynomial equation to the experimental data, according to the selected experimental
158 design. For this research, a full factorial three level experimental design (3^2) was
159 selected for both MAE and PLE extraction methodologies, and this design was tested
160 in both mushroom species. Two factors were analyzed for both extractions:
161 temperature (50-180°C) and time (5-30 min), and the variable responses investigated
162 were the total carbohydrate content of the crude extracts and the polysaccharide yield
163 after precipitation with cold ethanol (3:1; v/v). In total, eleven experiments were
164 conducted in a randomized order for each extraction technique and sample: nine points
165 of the factorial design and two additional center points to consider the experimental
166 errors. The experimental matrix design for both extraction methods is detailed in Table
167 1 (*P. ostreatus*) and Table 2 (*G. lucidum*). Optimal MAE and PLE extraction conditions
168 were estimated by multiple linear regressions using Statgraphics Centurion XVI
169 software (Statpoint Technologies, Warrenton, Virginia, USA).

170 **2.5. Total carbohydrate determination**

171 The total carbohydrate content of each extract obtained was measured by the phenol-
172 sulphuric acid method that was adapted from Dubois et al. (1951). Basically, 25 μ L of
173 diluted extract of *P. ostreatus* (1:30) and *G. lucidum* (1:15), of every tested extraction
174 condition, was added in triplicate, to a 96-well plate, plus 25 μ L of 5% phenol (Sigma-
175 Aldrich, Spain) solution and 125 μ L of concentrated H₂SO₄ (Panreac, Barcelona,
176 Spain). A standard curve of D-glucose (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain), from 0.032 to 0.8
177 mg/mL, was also prepared and added to the plate. After that, the plate was sealed and
178 incubated in a water bath at 80°C, for 30 min. The absorbance was read using the
179 M200 Plate Reader (Tecan, Mannedorf, Switzerland) at 490 nm and the results are
180 expressed as equivalents of glucose (mg/mL).

181 **2.6. Recovery of polysaccharides from extracts**

182 The polysaccharides were recovered from MAE and PLE extracts by adding three
183 volumes of ethanol and keeping under vigorous agitation for one minute. The mixtures
184 were kept at 4°C overnight to complete precipitation. Later on, the samples were
185 centrifuged (10,000 rpm, at 10°C, for 15 min) and the precipitate of each extract was
186 lyophilized to determine the polysaccharide yield.

187 **2.7. β -D-Glucans fluorimetric determination**

188 The β -D-glucans content was determined by fluorescence after complexation with
189 aniline blue diammonion salt (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain). According to Evans, Hoyne, &
190 Stone (1984), sirofluor is a fluorochrome present in aniline blue dye, that emits
191 fluorescence after forming complex with some polysaccharides. The branched
192 (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucans (bearing one single-unit at the branches) and linear (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -
193 D-glucans emit moderate to high fluorescence, when they are in single-helix
194 conformation. Therefore, this method can be used to determine the content of
195 mushroom β -D-glucans. The approach was based on Ko & Lin (2004) with slight
196 modifications: sample was solubilised in 0.05 M NaOH plus NaBH₄ (0.5 mM) at the
197 concentration of 0.02 mg/mL. In the reaction tube 300 μ L of sample was mixed with 30
198 μ L of 6 M NaOH and 630 μ L of dye mix (0.1% aniline blue: 1 M HCl: 1 M glycine/NaOH
199 buffer pH 9.5; 33:18:49). The mixture was incubated in water bath at 50°C, for 30 min.
200 Later on, each sample/standard (250 μ L) was transferred to a 96-well plate and
201 analyzed using a M200 Plate Reader (Tecan, Mannedorf, Switzerland) (excitation 398
202 nm and emission 502 nm). Curdlan (from *Alcaligenes faecalis*, Sigma-Aldrich, Spain)
203 was used as linear (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucan standard; and a chemically characterized glucan
204 named B1316PP (Smiderle et al., 2008) was used as branched (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-
205 glucan standard.

206 **2.8. Chitin content determination**

207 The chitin content of the optimized extracts was determined by a colorimetric method
208 based on Rementeria et al. (1991) and Rondle & Morgan (1955). Briefly, each extract
209 (5 mg) was hydrolyzed with 6 M HCl at 100°C for 2 h and adjusted to pH 10.0 after
210 cooling down. The hydrolyzed extract (0.5 mL) was used for the colorimetric method
211 according to Rementeria et al. (1991). Samples were read at 530 nm using a Evolution
212 600 UV-Vis (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Spain) spectrophotometer and glucosamine
213 (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain) was used as standard curve.

214 **2.9. Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy**

215 NMR spectra (^1H and HSQC) were obtained using a 400 MHz Bruker Avance III
216 spectrometer with a 5 mm inverse probe. The analyses were performed at 70°C in
217 $\text{Me}_2\text{SO}-d_6$, and the chemical shifts are expressed in δ (ppm) relative to $\text{Me}_2\text{SO}-d_6$ at δ
218 39.7 (^{13}C) and 2.40 (^1H).

219 **2.10. Analysis of monosaccharide composition by GC-MS**

220 The optimized extracts (1 mg) were hydrolyzed with 2 M TFA at 100°C for 8 h, followed
221 by evaporation to dryness. The dried carbohydrate samples were dissolved in 0.5 N
222 NH_4OH (100 μL), held at room temperature for 10–15 min in reinforced 4 ml Pyrex
223 tubes with Teflon lined screw caps. NaBH_4 (1 mg) was added, and the solution was
224 maintained at 100°C for 10 min, in order to reduce aldoses to alditols (Sasaki et al.,
225 2008). The product was dried and excess NaBH_4 was neutralized by the addition of
226 acetic acid or 1M TFA (100 μL), which was removed following the addition of methanol
227 (x 2) under a N_2 stream in a fume hood. Acetylation of the Me-alditols was performed in
228 pyridine– Ac_2O (200 μL ; 1:1, v/v), heated for 30 min at 100°C. The resulting alditol
229 acetates were analyzed by GC-MS, and identified by their typical retention times and
230 electron impact profiles. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was
231 performed using a Varian (model 3300) gas chromatograph linked to a Finnigan Ion-
232 Trap model 810 R-12 mass spectrometer, with He as carrier gas. A capillary column
233 (30 m x 0.25 mm i.d.) of DB-225, held at 50°C during injection and then programmed at

234 40°C/min to 220°C or 210°C (constant temperature) was used for qualitative and
 235 quantitative analysis of alditol acetates and partially O-methylated alditol acetates,
 236 respectively (Sasaki, Gorin, Souza, Czelusniak, & Iacomini, 2005).

237 **2.11. Statistical analysis**

238 The differences were evaluated at a 95% confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$) between optimal
 239 values obtained by MAE and PLE, using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)
 240 followed by Bonferroni's Multiple Comparison test, or two-way ANOVA. The graphs
 241 were drawn and the statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism version
 242 5.01 for Windows (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA).

243

244 **3. Results and Discussion**

245 **3.1. RSM analysis of MAE and PLE extraction conditions**

246 The full factorial 3^2 design was applied to each extraction method (MAE and PLE)
 247 covering nearly the full range of operation, but working always below the temperature
 248 and pressure limits of each equipment. This methodology was applied to maximize the
 249 amount of extracted β -glucans, considering the variables (polysaccharide yield and
 250 total carbohydrate content) equally important. The results obtained for all studied
 251 variables, using both MAE and PLE technologies, are detailed in table 1 for *P.*
 252 *ostreatus* and in table 2 for *G. lucidum*.

253

254 Table 1: Full factorial 3^2 experimental design of *P. ostreatus* extraction methods.

255 Predicted and observed values of each individual response.

Run	Independent factors		Investigated responses			
	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)	Yield (% w/w)		Total CHO ³ (eq. Glc, mg/mL)	
			MAE ¹	PLE ²	MAE ¹	PLE ²
1	50	5	5.6	5.3	6.2	3.9
2	50	17.5	6.4	3.3	7.5	3.2
3	50	30	7.4	11.1	8.0	5.9
4	115	5	11.4	3.7	8.1	1.9
5	115	17.5	11.4	2.8	6.9	1.0
6	115	30	13.0	2.5	6.6	1.60
7	180	5	28.4	23.0	10.7	6.3

8	180	17.5	31.2	37.0	11.7	10.6
9	180	30	32.4	30.3	16.5	7.7
10	115	17.5	12.0	3.0	7.8	1.5
11	115	17.5	12.8	3.6	7.4	1.8

Optimized desirability for MAE: 0.93. Optimal conditions: 180°C and 30 min
Optimized desirability for PLE: 0.82. Optimal conditions: 180°C and 26 min

Response	Predicted		Observed	
	MAE ¹	PLE ²	MAE ¹	PLE ²
Yield (% w/w)	32.4	32.0	33.6 ± 2.31	40.0 ± 6.95
Total CHO ³ (eq. Glc, mg/mL)	15.1	8.6	10.3 ± 0.96*	11.7 ± 2.21

256 ¹ Microwave-assisted extraction

257 ² Pressurized liquid extraction

258 ³ Total carbohydrates

259 * Significantly different from predicted value (p-value < 0.05)

260

261 Table 2: Full factorial 3² experimental design of *G. lucidum* extraction methods.

262 Predicted and observed values of each individual response.

Independent factors			Investigated responses			
Run	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)	Yield (% w/w)		Total CHO ³ (eq. Glc, mg/mL)	
			MAE ¹	PLE ²	MAE ¹	PLE ²
1	50	5	2.0	0.2	2.8	0.2
2	50	17.5	2.4	0.2	2.6	0.3
3	50	30	2.4	0.3	2.5	0.3
4	115	5	2.4	0.8	2.6	0.4
5	115	17.5	2.4	0.9	2.7	0.5
6	115	30	2.4	1.0	2.6	0.6
7	180	5	7.1	10.7	5.2	5.1
8	180	17.5	11.9	11.9	11.3	7.8
9	180	30	10.8	8.0	8.2	8.4
10	115	17.5	2.4	0.9	3.0	0.5
11	115	17.5	1.8	1.0	1.1	0.4

Optimized desirability for MAE: 0.86. Optimal conditions: 180°C and 27 min

Optimized desirability for PLE: 0.88. Optimal conditions: 180°C and 22 min

Response	Predicted		Observed	
	MAE ¹	PLE ²	MAE ¹	PLE ²
Yield (% w/w)	11.2	10.1	10.2 ± 0.35*	10.5 ± 1.12
Total CHO ³ (eq. Glc, mg/mL)	9.2	7.8	7.6 ± 0.14*	7.6 ± 0.53

263 ¹ Microwave-assisted extraction

264 ² Pressurized liquid extraction

265 ³ Total carbohydrates

266 * Significantly different from predicted value (p-value < 0.05)

267

268 An ANOVA test was performed for each response in order to fit and optimize the

269 statistical models corresponding to the desirability function, which allows the

270 simultaneous optimization of several responses. Response surface 3D plots are

271 depicted in figure 1. Water was chosen as solvent because it effectively extracts

272 polysaccharides. Furthermore, when submitted to subcritical conditions, water is able

273 to extract hydrophobic compounds and also insoluble polysaccharides such as linear β -
 274 glucans and chitins (Plaza & Turner, 2015). According to the results (Fig. 1), both
 275 mushroom species showed a similar behavior: the temperature has a strong positive
 276 influence in the polysaccharide extraction, while the increase in the extraction time
 277 slightly affected the polysaccharide yield, using both extraction methods. Temperature
 278 affects the mass transfer rate and its elevation associated with pressure (that maintains
 279 water in the liquid state) favors extraction, enhancing solubility of the solute and the
 280 diffusion coefficient. The thermal stability of the polysaccharides can be observed by
 281 their increasing yield (Fig. 1), even in the highest temperature tested. According to
 282 these results, it could be concluded that no degradation occurred. Besides, some other
 283 authors encountered that polysaccharide hydrolysis by subcritical water happens
 284 above 190°C (Novo, Bras, García, Belgacem, & Curvelo, 2015; Prado, Lachos-Perez,
 285 Forster-Carneiro, & Rostagno, 2016; Rogalinski, Liu, Albrecht, & Brunner, 2008; Yang
 286 et al., 2013).

287

288

289 **Figure 1:** Response surface 3D plots (desirability function) of MAE and PLE extracts of
 290 *P. ostreatus* and *G. lucidum*. Variable responses investigated: total carbohydrate

291 content of the crude extracts and the polysaccharide yield after precipitation with cold
292 ethanol (3:1; v/v).

293

294 Among the tested temperatures and times set for this research, the optimal MAE
295 conditions given by the model were 180°C and 30 min for *P. ostreatus*; and 180°C and
296 27 min for *G. lucidum*. The optimal conditions and predicted values were determined
297 on the basis of the desirability functions, which were 0.93 and 0.86, respectively. For
298 PLE extractions, the best conditions were 180°C and 26 min for *P. ostreatus*; and
299 180°C and 22 min for *G. lucidum*, considering the same interval of temperature and
300 time tested. The desirability functions were 0.82 and 0.88, respectively. In order to
301 confirm the predicted results for the optimal conditions, three further experiments were
302 performed for each species and each extraction method. A hypothesis test was applied
303 to evaluate the accuracy between theoretical and experimental results, using a 95%
304 confidence interval. The results are presented in tables 1 and 2 for *P. ostreatus* and *G.*
305 *lucidum*, respectively.

306 Normally, for insoluble compounds higher temperatures promote higher extracted
307 yields (Plaza & Turner, 2015). This pattern was observed in all cases, except for *P.*
308 *ostreatus*, using PLE, that showed a slight yield increase at very low temperatures
309 followed by a decrease and a second enlargement, while the other extractions showed
310 a growing yield increase from 50°C to 180°C (tables 1 and 2).

311 Some reports suggested that pressure has very little influence on the properties of
312 water, as long as it remains in the liquid state. However, higher pressure may help wet
313 the sample matrix, resulting in improved extraction efficiency (Plaza & Turner, 2015).
314 Based on this statement, PLE (pressure: 10.2-11.7 MPa) should be more effective than
315 MAE (maximum pressure: 1.5 MPa) in extracting polysaccharides. Nevertheless, only a
316 slight difference was observed for *P. ostreatus*, and no significant difference was
317 noticed for *G. lucidum* extracts at the optimal conditions of the two methods (Fig. 2),

318 when the polysaccharide yield and total carbohydrate content were compared. Perhaps
 319 other physical or chemical characteristics of each mushroom might influence the
 320 extraction and, consequently, the obtained products as well.

321

322

323 **Figure 2:** Comparison among the yield of polysaccharides and total carbohydrate
 324 content of the extracts of *P. ostreatus* and *G. lucidum*, using MAE and PLE. Statistical
 325 analyses were performed by means of two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed
 326 by Bonferroni's test. Data are expressed as means \pm SEM; * $p < 0.05$.

327

328 Furthermore polysaccharide yields extracted from *P. ostreatus* were 23-30% larger
 329 than the obtained from *G. lucidum*, using both extraction methods (Fig. 2). This can be
 330 explained by the high content of insoluble polysaccharides, or fibers, present in *G.*
 331 *lucidum* (59.16%) as described by Mau et al. (2001). The larger amount of these fibers
 332 might require stronger extraction conditions to break the hydrogen bonds and remove
 333 such insoluble polysaccharides from the fungal matrix. In the case of *P. ostreatus*, the
 334 higher amount of soluble polysaccharides (47%) and lower content of fibers (9.4%), as
 335 determined by Bonatti et al. (2004), facilitates the extraction of β -glucans and other
 336 biologically active polysaccharides.

337 On the other hand, both species extracted using MAE and PLE technologies provided
 338 higher polysaccharide yields than using normal hot water extractions. *Pleurotus* spp.
 339 have yielded around 6.0 to 16.0% of polysaccharide crude extract (cold and hot water
 340 extractions) (Carbonero et al., 2012; Santos-Neves et al., 2008b), while *Ganoderma*
 341 spp. yielded 1.0 to 7.1% (cold and hot water extractions) (Amaral et al., 2008; Li et al.,
 342 2016). These results showed that extractions combining pressure and elevated
 343 temperatures (above the boiling point of water) are effective methods to extract
 344 polysaccharides from mushrooms without using pollutant solvents.

345 3.2. Chemical characterization of the optimized extracts

346 The monosaccharide composition of the extracts obtained at optimal conditions for
 347 MAE and PLE were analyzed by GC-MS (Table 3), the anomericity and linkage types
 348 of the polysaccharides present in the extracts were determined by NMR spectroscopy,
 349 and the β -glucans were quantitatively analyzed by fluorimetric assays.

350

351 Table 3: Monosaccharide composition of the extracts obtained from *P. ostreatus* and
 352 *G. lucidum*.

		Monosaccharides (%) ¹			
Fractions		Glucose	Mannose	Galactose	3-O-Me-Galactose
<i>P. ostreatus</i>	MAE	91.0	4.9	3.5	Tr. ²
	PLE	91.3	6.1	2.4	Tr. ²
<i>G. lucidum</i>	MAE	89.6	7.1	1.1	-
	PLE	86.5	9.4	1.8	-

353 ¹ Alditol acetates obtained on successive hydrolysis, NaBH₄ reduction, and acetylation.

354 ² Tr. \leq 0.6%.

355

356 In comparison with the literature data, the HSQC spectra (Figs. 3 and 4) of each extract
 357 showed that all of them contained a mixture of polysaccharides, including β -glucans, α -
 358 glucans, an heteropolysaccharide composed by mannose and galactose and also
 359 oligosaccharides. Previous works about the isolation and characterization of mushroom
 360 polysaccharides confirmed these results (Ruthes et al., 2016; Ruthes et al., 2015).
 361 Signals of trehalose (δ 93.0/4.82 ppm and 93.1/4.81 ppm) were observed in both *P.*

362 *ostreatus* extracts. This disaccharide, also known as mycose (the mushroom sugar), is
363 present in a variety of living organisms and it is used to overcome stress conditions as
364 heat, cold, desiccation and so forth, because of its capacity of stabilizing proteins as
365 well as lipid bilayer (Jain & Roy, 2009). *G. lucidum* extracts did not present trehalose,
366 although they also presented low molecular weight carbohydrates, identified by the pair
367 of reducing units signals from δ 91.5 to 92.2/4.83 to 4.89 ($^{13}\text{C}/^1\text{H}$) and from δ 96.0 to
368 96.9/4.20 to 4.29 ($^{13}\text{C}/^1\text{H}$) (Bubb, 2003).
369

370

371

372 **Figure 3:** HSQC spectra of *P. ostreatus* extracts, using MAE (A) and PLE (B).373 Experiments were performed in Me₂SO-*d*₆ at 70°C (chemical shifts are expressed in δ

374 ppm).

375

376 Apart from this, the extracts of both species were composed mainly by glucose, more
377 than 86% (Table 3), confirming that mushroom extracts are rich in glucan
378 polysaccharides, which have been effectively recovered by the tested methods. A large
379 number of studies on the polysaccharides of *Pleurotus* spp. and *Ganoderma* spp. have
380 encountered β -glucans (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)-linked, linear α -glucans (1 \rightarrow 3)-linked (in *G.*
381 *lucidum*), and a branched α/β -glucan (1 \rightarrow 3)-linked (in *P. florida*) (Ruthes et al., 2015).
382 The NMR signals observed in the HSQC anomeric regions of both mushrooms (Figs. 3
383 and 4) are characteristic of these linkages. The signals arising from δ 102.7 to 103.5
384 ppm for ^{13}C and from δ 4.13 to 4.43 ppm for ^1H confirmed the C-1 of glucans in β -
385 configuration (Liu et al., 2014). While the signals arising from δ 99.6 to 100.1 ppm for
386 ^{13}C and from δ 4.97 to 4.98 ppm for ^1H confirmed the C-1 of glucans in α -configuration
387 (Santos-Neves et al., 2008a). Signals at the range of δ 86.1 to 87.3 ppm for ^{13}C and
388 from δ 3.16 to 3.39 ppm for ^1H arose from C-3 O-substituted of β -linkages (Liu et al.,
389 2014); and the signals of C-3 relative to the O-substituted α -linkages have appeared at
390 δ ~83.3/3.55 ppm ($^{13}\text{C}/^1\text{H}$) (Santos-Neves et al., 2008a), confirming that all extracts
391 contain α - and β -glucans (1 \rightarrow 3)-linked. The high intensity of signals at δ ~68.4 ppm of
392 the spectra strongly indicates the presence of (1 \rightarrow 6)-linkages.
393

396 **Figure 4:** HSQC spectra of *G. lucidum* extracts, using MAE (A) and PLE (B).

397 Experiments were performed in $\text{Me}_2\text{SO}-d_6$ at 70°C (chemical shifts are expressed in δ

398 ppm).

399

400 Besides glucose, all the extracts contain mannose (4.9 - 9.4%) and small amounts of
401 galactose (1.1 - 3.5%). The presence of heteropolysaccharides composed of mannose
402 and galactose is frequently reported on literature (Smiderle et al., 2008; Zhang, Xu, Fu,
403 & Sun, 2013). Usually, many species of basidiomycetes present mannogalactans or
404 similar heteropolysaccharides, which may vary in branching degree, presence or
405 absence of fucose and also methyl groups substituting some galactose residues. In all
406 the spectra, signals relative to β -mannopyranose were identified at δ 101.2-101.6/4.82-
407 4.84 ($^{13}\text{C}/^1\text{H}$). Signals of galactose were less evident in *G. lucidum* than in *P. ostreatus*
408 spectra, although the presence of α -galactopyranose could be recognized in all of the
409 extracts. Low signals of methyl were noticed only for *P. ostreatus*, which was confirmed
410 by traces of 3-O-methyl-galactose observed on GC-MS analysis (Table 3). No signals
411 of proteins or carboxylic acids were detected in any extract.

412 The main difference between the species seems to be the proportion of each
413 polysaccharide extracted, especially the class of glucans (branched or linear; α or β -
414 configuration; and linkage types), although this cannot be precisely quantified by NMR.
415 Therefore, a quantitative analysis was made using a fluorimetric assay. According to
416 the literature, the most common glucan found in mushrooms is the (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -
417 glucan containing one-single unit at the branching point (Ruthes et al., 2015). This
418 polysaccharide exhibits moderate fluorescence when compared to the linear (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -
419 glucan, after complexation with sirofluor. Therefore, these two β -glucans (B1316PP
420 and curdlan, respectively) were used as standard for the fluorimetric assay, with the
421 aim of comparing the fluorescence emitted by the extracts. The extracts emitted less
422 than 40% of the fluorescence emitted by the curdlan (data not shown), at the same
423 concentration. Although, when compared to the branched glucan B1316PP, *P.*
424 *ostreatus* extracts showed 87% and 93.7% (respect. for MAE and PLE), and *G.*
425 *lucidum* extracts presented 60.7% and 76% (respect. for MAE and PLE) of the
426 B1316PP fluorescence. These results, in combination with the NMR data, indicates

427 that the majority of the β -glucans in *P. ostreatus* are similar to the B1316PP, while *G.*
 428 *lucidum* extracts may present lower concentration, or the glucans present in this
 429 species are more branched, inducing lower fluorescence, as observed by Evans et al.
 430 (1984). No significant difference between the extraction methods was noticed for *P.*
 431 *ostreatus* regarding the type of β -glucans extracted. However for *G. lucidum*, PLE
 432 extract showed significant more fluorescence than MAE extract, indicating that this
 433 procedure was more efficient in extracting its β -glucans (Fig. 5).
 434

435
 436 **Figure 5:** Fluorescence observed after complexation of sirofluor with the extracts of *P.*
 437 *ostreatus* (MAE and PLE) and *G. lucidum* (MAE and PLE). Values were determined in
 438 relation to the fluorescence of B1316PP. Statistical analyses were performed by means
 439 of one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Bonferroni's test. Data are
 440 expressed as means \pm SEM; *p < 0.05.

441
 442 PLE operated within pressure almost 10 times higher than MAE, therefore this
 443 condition may facilitate extraction of *G. lucidum* polysaccharides, from its hard texture
 444 (harder than *P. ostreatus* and other edible mushrooms). It is important to observe that
 445 the extraction conditions should be carefully evaluated and determined for each
 446 species according to the purpose and target components.

447 The amount of chitins was determined by colorimetric method, and *P. ostreatus* extract
448 obtained by MAE contained 2.1% chitins while PLE extracted 1.4%. The extracts from
449 *G. lucidum* showed respectively 2.4% and 1.3% for MAE and PLE extracts. Chitin is
450 one of the major fibers of mushrooms, reaching values close/above to 20% dry weight,
451 depending on the species (Wu, Zivanovic, Draughon, & Sams, 2004) therefore, the low
452 amount of chitins observed for MAE and PLE extracts indicates that this
453 polysaccharide was not efficiently extracted from the fungal matrix. The use of stronger
454 extraction conditions such as longer time or alkaline solvents should be considered and
455 studied in order to promote their extraction and/or other insoluble polysaccharides
456 present in mushrooms.

457

458 **Concluding remarks**

459 The data obtained with this research showed that temperature is the key factor on
460 extracting polysaccharides from mushrooms, using MAE or PLE methods. According to
461 our results, higher temperatures showed higher yields. At the optimal conditions,
462 similar total polysaccharide yields were recovered from *G. lucidum* and slightly different
463 yields from *P. ostreatus*, comparing both methods. Both procedures were efficient in
464 extracting β -glucans, however the content of β -glucans was equal in *P. ostreatus*
465 extracts, and significantly different for *G. lucidum* extracts, according to the fluorimetric
466 assays. PLE has the advantage of recovering the extract directly in a vessel without the
467 necessity of centrifugation, while MAE requires separating the extract from residue. On
468 the other hand, PLE showed lower reproducibility than MAE and consequently lower
469 desirability when was tested with *P. ostreatus*. The main difference between extracts
470 obtained from the selected species seems to be the different concentration of each
471 polysaccharide extracted, under similar conditions, particularly regarding the different
472 glucans obtained. Both extraction systems (MAE and PLE) presented advantages and
473 disadvantages, but both showed to be easy, fast and efficient approaches to extract

474 mushroom β -glucans. Nevertheless, each sample/mushroom species may require a
475 careful study to determine the best conditions based on its physical and chemical
476 characteristics. The use of stronger extraction conditions such as longer time or
477 alkaline solvents should be considered if the target molecules are highly insoluble.
478

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- 650

Table 1: Full factorial 3² experimental design of *P. ostreatus* extraction methods. Predicted and observed values of each individual response.

Independent factors			Investigated responses			
Run	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)	Yield (% w/w)		Total CHO ³ (eq. Glc, mg/mL)	
			MAE ¹	PLE ²	MAE ¹	PLE ²
1	50	5	5.6	5.3	6.2	3.9
2	50	17.5	6.4	3.3	7.5	3.2
3	50	30	7.4	11.1	8.0	5.9
4	115	5	11.4	3.7	8.1	1.9
5	115	17.5	11.4	2.8	6.9	1.0
6	115	30	13.0	2.5	6.6	1.60
7	180	5	28.4	23.0	10.7	6.3
8	180	17.5	31.2	37.0	11.7	10.6
9	180	30	32.4	30.3	16.5	7.7
10	115	17.5	12.0	3.0	7.8	1.5
11	115	17.5	12.8	3.6	7.4	1.8
Optimized desirability for MAE: 0.93. Optimal conditions: 180°C and 30 min						
Optimized desirability for PLE: 0.82. Optimal conditions: 180°C and 26 min						
Response		Predicted		Observed		
		MAE ¹	PLE ²	MAE ¹	PLE ²	
Yield (% w/w)		32.4	32.0	33.6 ± 2.31	40.0 ± 6.95	
Total CHO ³ (eq. Glc, mg/mL)		15.1	8.6	10.3 ± 0.96*	11.7 ± 2.21	

¹ Microwave-assisted extraction

² Pressurized liquid extraction

³ Total carbohydrates

* Significantly different from predicted value (p-value < 0.05)

Table 2: Full factorial 3² experimental design of *G. lucidum* extraction methods. Predicted and observed values of each individual response.

Independent factors			Investigated responses			
Run	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)	Yield (% w/w)		Total CHO ³ (eq. Glc, mg/mL)	
			MAE ¹	PLE ²	MAE ¹	PLE ²
1	50	5	2.0	0.2	2.8	0.2
2	50	17.5	2.4	0.2	2.6	0.3
3	50	30	2.4	0.3	2.5	0.3
4	115	5	2.4	0.8	2.6	0.4
5	115	17.5	2.4	0.9	2.7	0.5
6	115	30	2.4	1.0	2.6	0.6
7	180	5	7.1	10.7	5.2	5.1
8	180	17.5	11.9	11.9	11.3	7.8
9	180	30	10.8	8.0	8.2	8.4
10	115	17.5	2.4	0.9	3.0	0.5
11	115	17.5	1.8	1.0	1.1	0.4
Optimized desirability for MAE: 0.86. Optimal conditions: 180°C and 27 min						
Optimized desirability for PLE: 0.88. Optimal conditions: 180°C and 22 min						
Response		Predicted		Observed		
		MAE ¹	PLE ²	MAE ¹	PLE ²	
Yield (% w/w)		11.2	10.1	10.2 ± 0.35*	10.5 ± 1.12	
Total CHO ³ (eq. Glc, mg/mL)		9.2	7.8	7.6 ± 0.14*	7.6 ± 0.53	

¹ Microwave-assisted extraction

² Pressurized liquid extraction

³ Total carbohydrates

* Significantly different from predicted value (p-value < 0.05)

Table 3: Monosaccharide composition of the extracts obtained from *P. ostreatus* and *G. lucidum*.

		Monosaccharides (%) ¹			
Fractions		Glucose	Mannose	Galactose	3-O-Me-Galactose
<i>P. ostreatus</i>	MAE	91.0	4.9	3.5	Tr. ²
	PLE	91.3	6.1	2.4	Tr. ²
<i>G. lucidum</i>	MAE	89.6	7.1	1.1	-
	PLE	86.5	9.4	1.8	-

¹ Alditol acetates obtained on successive hydrolysis, NaBH₄ reduction, and acetylation.

² Tr. ≤ 0.6%.

Figure(s)

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Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Figure(s)

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